

Synthesis of $Ag_xCu_{(1-x)}Fe_2O_4$ thin films and Study of the Change in Some of Their Optical and Electrical Properties Due to the Change of Molar Concentration

Mubarak Dirar Abdalla Yagoup¹, Safwa.Yagoub^{#2}, Lamiaa Galal Amin^{#3}, Nuha. Allam^{#4}, A . H. Abdelrhman⁵

1 Department of Physics, College of Science, Sudan University of Science and Technology, Khartoum, Sudan

2 Physics Department, College of Science, Northern Border University, Arar, Saudi Arabia

3 Physics Department, College of Science, Northern Border University, Arar, Saudi Arabia

4 Chemistry Department, College of Science, Northern Border University, Arar, Saudi Arabia

5 Department of Physics, College of Science, Qassim University, Buridah, Saudi Arabia

Abstract— Five samples of $Ag_xCu_{(1-x)}Fe_2O_4$ having molar concentrations $x=0.1,0.3,0.5,0.7,0.9$ were prepared. The optical properties of them were studied. The crystal structure was determined using the XRD technique indicating that the crystal nano spacing decreases upon decreasing the concentration of Cu and increasing the Ag concentration x . The UV-VIS spectrometer results showed that the absorbance increases upon increasing the Ag concentration and decreasing the Cu concentration. The transmission decreases when the Ag concentration increases, which is associated with the decrease of Cu concentration. The FTIR results showed that the transmission to Infrared radiation increases as the Ag concentration decreases and the Cu concentration increases.

Keywords— XRD, FTIR analysis, UV-VIS spectroscopy, energy gap, copper.

I. INTRODUCTION

The optical properties of matter like scattering, absorption, transmission, and reflection play an important role in our lives [1,2]. The electrical and optical properties rely heavily on the electron transitions between energy levels or energy bands [3,4,5]. The electrons transition between energy levels and bands are responsible for absorption and emission processes, which are related to the reflection and refraction processes [6,7,8]. This indicates that the changes in the energy levels or band structure can change the optical properties of matter [9,10,11]. Unfortunately, the change of the optical for bulk matter to satisfy the required technological needs is extremely difficult. This forces scientists to use a new approach based on nanoscience [12].

Nanoscience is concerned with the study, of nanomaterials. Nanomaterials are in the form of a very large number of isolated particles having dimensions ranging from one nanometre up to three hundred nanometres. Nanomaterials cannot be described using classical laws but can be described using the laws of quantum mechanics [13]. Changing the nano size, geometry, chemical composition, and concentration can change the physical properties of the nanomaterial. This is because changing these parameters changes the band structure and the atomic bonds according to the quantum laws [14].

The optical properties of matter are widely used in energy generation. The most popular energy generation technology is the one based on solar energy technology. The most preferred one is the one that converts solar energy to electricity. This comes from the fact that electric energy can be converted easily to other useful energy forms. The commercially available cells are silicon solar cells which are expensive and have

complex fabrication processes. This encourages to search for new cell types [15]. Nano-solar cells represent the best candidate [16]. Different nano cells were suggested including polymer cells, and zinc and copper oxide cells [17].

The work done by M. Schnaiter et al [18]. use a long path extinction spectrometer (LOPES) to determine the absorption coefficient for aerosols. The results obtained found that the absorption coefficient is dependent on the wavelength The absorption coefficient decreases upon increasing the wavelength for large wavelengths. The results of Giorgio Dall'Olmo, et al [19] indicated that in the surface open ocean, the absorption coefficient of chromophoric dissolved organic matter decreases upon increasing wavelength. The wavelength range is (400-950nm) Herve Claustre et al [20] studied the absorption coefficient of phytoplankton, nonalgal particles, and dissolved organic matter in coastal waters around Europe. They found that the absorption coefficient decreases when the wavelength increases in the range (400-750nm). In their work, Anette, Karlsson, et al indicated that the absorption coefficient decreases when the wavelength increases for mechanical pulps [21]. The paper of Ernesto, et al showed that the elemental carbon (EC) concentration increase caused the atmospheric absorption coefficient of light to increase also [22]. The relation between wavelength and absorption coefficient of E. Weingartner, et al [23] indicated also that increasing the wavelength decreases the absorption coefficient for soot particles using an aethalometer.

Ahmed A. A. et al [24] studied the properties of thin films formed when ZnS was doped with Al. The results obtained showed that changing AL concentration changes the absorption coefficient. The same samples were tested by M. H. Eisa et al [25] to show that the ZnAl is in the form of nanoparticles. The morphology of these samples when studied by Ahmed and others again [26] indicates the change of the roughness with the change of AL concentration. Such roughness affects the absorption coefficient. The fact that thin films nano materials play an important role in modern technology encourages us to do this work, where sections 2 and 3 are concerned with the experimental procedures and results. Sections 4 and 5 are devoted to discussion and conclusion

II. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

Sliver nitrate [$\text{Ag}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ (96%)], Copper nitrate hexahydrate [$\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (99%)], Iron nitrate [$\text{Fe}(\text{NO}_3)_3$ (98%)] and Nitric Acid (HNO_3 , 99% were used as raw materials. All materials were reagent graded and distilled water was used in the preparation process.

Fig.1 PH Meter and Sensitive plans images

Fig. 2 image of furnace Vulcan

Sol-gel method

Five samples of $Ag_x Cu_{(1-x)} Fe_2O_4$ were prepared in different concentrations using the sol-gel method. The amount of metal nitrates in distilled water was homogenised and separatism of metal ions were achieved by the use of sodium hydroxide. A required amount of nitric acid was added into the solution in order to modify pH value to be less than 5. The solution was constantly stirred and heated at $80^\circ C$ in a magnetic stirrer for an hour to condensate into a gel. The obtained sol was then kept for 24 hours at room temperature to avoid reverse interactions, the samples were dried at $300^\circ C$ for 3 hours to get powder.

Then, the obtained powders were grained by agate mortar and finally sintered at 750°C for 4 h in a programmable furnace to remove any organic material present in samples. The final products were characterized using X-ray diffraction (XRD), and UV-VIS spectrometer.

- Compounds ($\text{Ag}_x\text{Cu}_{1-x}\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_4$) were prepared using the gel-sol method at the concentrations shown.
- The study was carried out using XRD technology, through which its crystalline and nanostructure, its lattice parameters, and the locations of atoms inside the cell were determined.
- Ultraviolet-visible radiation was used to evaluate the band gap and optical and electrical properties.
- The type of chemical bonds within atoms was determined using FTIR.
- The results of the studies were recorded in tables and presented graphically.

III.RESULTS

In this work, the results of an examination of ($\text{Ag}_x\text{Cu}_{(1-x)}\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_4$) (0.1,0.3,0.5,0.7 and 0.9) are exhibited. The data of X-ray diffraction (XRD) have been recorded and displayed graphically using the Rietveld method to study their crystal nanostructure and their lattice parameters, the positions of atoms within the cell.

The UV-visible is used to evaluate the band gap and optical properties beside electrical and magnetic properties using absorption spectra beside a special computer program.

A -Xray diffraction results ($\text{Ag}_x\text{Cu}_{(1-x)}\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_4$) (0.1 ,0.3,0.5 ,0.7 and 0.9)

The crystal structure of all samples of the compound ($\text{Ag}_x\text{Cu}_{1-x}\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_4$) for various concentrations when exposed to X-rays is shown in Table (1)

TABLE I
lattice parameters of $\text{ag}_x\text{cu}_{1-x}\text{fe}_2\text{o}_4$ samples at different concentrations

B. UV-VIS Optical Results of ($\text{Ag}_x\text{Cu}_{1-x}\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_4$) samples:

XRD Data		$\text{Ag}_{0.1}\text{Cu}_{0.9}\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_4$	$\text{Ag}_{0.3}\text{Cu}_{0.7}\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_4$	$\text{Ag}_{0.5}\text{Cu}_{0.5}\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_4$	$\text{Ag}_{0.7}\text{Cu}_{0.3}\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_4$	$\text{Ag}_{0.9}\text{Cu}_{0.1}\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_4$
		4	4	4		4
Space Group		P63 / mc (194)				
Crystal System		Hexagonal	Hexagonal	Hexagonal	Hexagonal	Hexagonal
Cell Parameter s 10^{-10} m	A	3.039	3.039	3.039	3.039	3.039
	B	3.039	3.039	3.039	3.039	3.039
	C	12.395	12.395	12.395	12.395	12.395
Density ($\text{g}\cdot\text{cm}^{-3}$)		6.556	6.562	6.569	6.575	6.583
Volume (10^{-10}) ³		99.1376	99.1383	99.139	99.1397	99.1401
d (10^{-10} m)		1.75171	1.75166	1.75159	1.75153	1.75147
Cell Angle	Alpha	90	90	90	90	90
	Beta	90	90	90	90	90
	Gamm a	120	120	120	120	120

Fig. 3 Relation between absorbance and wavelengths of five ($Ag_xCu_{1-x}Fe_2O_4$)

Fig. 4 Relation between transmission and wavelengths of five ($Ag_xCu_{1-x}Fe_2O_4$) samples (0.1,0.3,0.5,0.7 and 0.9)

Fig. 5 Relation between reflection and wavelengths of five ($\text{Ag}_x\text{Co}_{1-x}\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_4$) samples (0.1 ,0.3,0.5 ,0.7, and 0.9) Molar concentrations

C. FTIR Results of ($\text{Ag}_x\text{Cu}_{1-x}\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_4$) (0.1 ,0.3,0.5 ,0.7 and 0.9)

TABLE II
DATA OF IR SPECTRUM FOR $\text{Ag}_x\text{Cu}_{1-x}\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_4$ SAMPLES

No	Peaks (cm^{-1})	Bonds	Functional Groups
1	475	O^{+2}	Met Oxide
2	887	C–H “loop”	Aromatics
3	1140	C–N stretch	aliphatic amines
4	1410	C–C stretch (in–ring)	Aromatics
5	1670	N–H bend	1° amines
6	3015	C–H stretch	Aromatics
7	3160	O–H stretch	carboxylic acids
8	3390	N–H stretch	1°, 2° amines, amides
9	3640	O–H stretch, free hydroxyl	alcohols, phenols
10	3780	O–H stretch	Water

Fig. 6 IR spectrum of $\text{Ag}_x\text{Cu}_{1-x}\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_4$ samples

IV. DISCUSS

The above results showed the optical and electrical properties of $\text{Ag}_x\text{Cu}_{1-x}\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_4$ for the molar concentrations $x=0.1, 0.3, 0.5, 0.7, 0.9$. Table (1) for XRD technique indicated that the crystal nano spacing d decreases upon increasing the molar concentration the crystal volume also decreases also upon increasing the concentration. However, the density increases upon increasing the concentration.

Using a UV-VIS spectrometer (figure (3)) explains the absorbance of $\text{Ag}_x\text{Cu}_{1-x}\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_4$ at different concentrations. absorbance value decreases from 1.00 (a.u) at wavelength 409.2 nm for $x=0.9$ sample to 0.52 (a.u) for $x=0.1$ at the same wavelength, which agrees with the fact that the decreases in absorbing surface lade result in a reduction of the absorbance at decrease at molar concentration. indicated that the absorbance increases upon increasing the molar concentration. Figure (4) shows the transmissivity of $\text{Ag}_x\text{Cu}_{1-x}\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_4$ at different concentrations. Transmissivity is the opposite process of absorption. We found the lowest transmissivity value at which the highest absorbance value is 409.5 in Figure (3). This confirms that transmissivity is the opposite process to absorbance. Figure (5) shows that the reflectivity at very long and very short wavelengths increases with increasing molar concentration. It is also noted that this material has good reflectivity in the 400-418 region, and the largest reflectivity values at the wavelength of 409.2 nm, so the energies at which the reflection occurred can be used as a mirrors that reflect these wavelengths. Also, Figure (5) indicated that the transmission to infrared. radiation decreases as molar concentration increases. The FTIR results in Figure (6) It was found that the basic vibrations such as 475 (cm^{-1}) and 887 cm^{-1} confirm that the material is a metal oxide, the basic vibrations 3160, 3640 and 3780 confirm the presence of the hydroxyl group O-H (they are very important because they represent catalysts for energy transfer through the material) indicated that the transmission to infrared. radiation decreases as molar concentration increases. The results obtained are in good agreement with some previous studies. The observed change of absorbance with the wavelength is confirmed by the work of Schnaiter [18], Giorgio [19], and Karlsson [21] which indicated that the absorption coefficient thus absorbance changes with the wavelength The observed change of absorbance with the change of Ag and Cu concentration was confirmed by the work of Ernesto [22] which shows that increasing carbon concentration increases

absorbance. Similarly, Ahmed [24,26] showed in his work that changing Al concentration changes absorbance.

V. CONCLUSIONS

The results obtained for the optical properties of ($\text{Ag}_x \text{Cu}_{(1-x)} \text{Fe}_2\text{O}_4$) samples showed that the crystal spacing, and transmission of infrared radiation decrease upon increasing the concentration of Ag and decreasing the concentration of Cu. In contrast, the absorbance and reflection increase when the Ag concentration is increased.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The authors would like to thank the Northern Border University, Sudan University of Science and Technology, and Qassim University for their contribution to this research work and its good production.

REFERENCES

- [1] Raymond A. Serway, physics for scientists and engineers with modern physics, Saunders College Publishing, USA (2004).
- [2] Paul Lorrain and Dale R. Corson, Electromagnetic fields and waves, W.H. Ferman and company San Francis co (1970).
- [3] Steven H. Simon, The Oxford Solid State Basics, Oxford University Press, United States of America,2013, ISBN 978-0-19-968076-4 (Hbk.)
- [4] C. Smedley; a. Ben Zvi; a. Borel; X Chang; C. Grimes; T. Rao; g. Sigalov; s. Woo. "Electron amplification in diamond." AIP Conference Proceedings. Vol. 877. No. 1. American Institute of Physics, 2006.
- [5] Devoret, Michel H., and Robert J. Schoelkopf. "Amplifying quantum signals with the single-electron transistor." Nature 406.6799 (2000).
- [6] G. Aruldas, Quantum Mechanics, and edition, PHI private limited, New Delhi (2009)
- [7] David J. Griffith, Introduction to quantum mechanics, Prentice Hall, New Jersey (2005).
- [8] Hartmut Haug, Stephan W Koch, Quantum Theory of the Optical and Electronic Properties of Semiconductors 5th Edition, Singapore,2009, <https://doi.org/10.1142/7184>.
- [9] Rohit P. Pavankumar, Antoinette J. Taylor, Optical Techniques for Solid-State Materials Characterization, Taylor France Group LLC, New York,2012.
- [10] Lesley E. Smart, Elaine A. Moore, Solid state chemistry: fourth edition, Tayler Francis Group, Boca Raton Florida, 2016. DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1201/b12047>
- [11] Richard J. D. Tilley, Understanding Solids: The Science of Materials, Edition. 3rd, Wiley, New York,2021, ISBN-13. 978-1119716501
- [12] [Edward L. Wolf, (2015), Nanophysics and Nanotechnology: An Introduction to Modern Concepts in Nanoscience, 3rd edition, Wiley-VCH, British,2015
- [13] Hussein, Nur Hafizah A. Khalid, Mirza, Nanotechnology For Smart Concrete, Taylor France Group LLC, New York,2022.
- [14] Li, B., Wang, L., Kang, B., and Qiu, Y., Solar Energy Materials and Solar Cells, Wiley-VCH, New York (2006)
- [15] Würfel. P. Physics of Solar Cells – From Principles of New Concepts., Wiley-VCH, New York
- [16] Lina Wang, Mavd P.R. Teles, Ahmad Arabkoohsar *, Haoshui Yu, Kamal A.R. Ismail b, Omid Mahian, Somchai Wongwises, A holistic and state-of-the-art review of nanotechnology in solar cells, y Elsevier Ltd, 54, December 2022, 102864.
- [17] Pontus Cronholm, Hanna L. Karlsson, Jonas Hedberg, Troy A. Lowe, Lina Wnnberg, Karine Elihn, Inger Odnevall Wallinder, and Lennart Möller, Intracellular Uptake and Toxicity of Ag and CuO Nanoparticles: A Comparison Between Nanoparticles and their Corresponding Metal Ions, wileyonlinelibrary.com, Vol. 9, No.7, P. 970-982,2013, <https://DOI.org/10.1002/sml.201201069>
- [18] Schnaiter, M., Schmid, O., Petzold, A., Fritzsche, L., Klein, K. F., Andreae, M. O., ... & Schurath, U. Measurement of wavelength-resolved light absorption by aerosols utilizing a UV-VIS extinction cell. Aerosol science and technology, (2005).
- [19] Giorgio Dall'olmo, * Robert J. W. Brewin, Francesco Nencioli, Emanuele Organelli, Ina Lefering, David Mckee, Rüdiger Röttgers, Catherine Mitchell, Emmanuel Boss, Annick Bricaud, And Gavin Tilstone. "Determination of the absorption coefficient of chromophoric dissolved organic matter from underway spectrophotometry." Optics Express 25.24 (2017).
- [20] Babin, M., D. Stramski, G. M. Ferrari, H. Claustre, A. Bricaud, G. Obolensky, and N. Hoepffner, Variations in the light absorption coefficients of phytoplankton, nonalgal particles, and dissolved organic matter in coastal waters around Europe, J. Geophys.Res., 108(C7), 3211, doi:10.1029/2001JC000882, 2003
- [21] Anette Karlsson, Sofia Enberg, Mats Rundlöf, Magnus Paulsson and Per Edström, "Determining optical properties of mechanical pulps." Nordic Pulp & Paper Research Journal 27.3 (2012).
- [22] Ernesto Gramsch, Isabel Ormeño, Guillermo Palma, Francisco Cereceda-Balic, Pedro Oyola. "Use of the light absorption coefficient to monitor elemental carbon and PM2. 5—example of Santiago de Chile." Journal of the Air & Waste Management Association 54:799 – 808 (2004).
- [23] E. Weingartner, H. Saathoff, M. Schnaiter N. Streit, B. Bittner, U. Baltensperger "Absorption of light by soot particles: determination of the absorption coefficient by means of nephelometers." Journal of Aerosol Science 34.10 (2003).
- [24] A. A. Ahmed, M. H. Eisaa, M. D. Abd-Alla, Study the optical parameters of aluminum doped ZnS films deposited on a soda-lime glass substrate, Chalcogenide Letters Vol. 19, No. 9, September 2022, p. 591 - 598
- [25] [M. H. Eisa, Structural characterization of synthesized Al-doped ZnS nanoparticles deposited on a glass substrate, Chalcogenide Letters Vol. 18, No. 12, December 2021, p. 783 - 789
- [26] A.A Ahmed and M D Abd Allah, the Morphological Properties of ZnS Nanoparticles Deposited on Glass Substrates as a Function of Aluminum Content, Juniper Online Journal Material Science ISSN: 2575-856X, Research Article Vol.7, No 2 - November 2022 DOI: 10.19080/JOJMS.2022.07.555708